

Purchasing Behavior of Rural Migrants: A Comparative Analysis of Sukkur and Khairpur Districts

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Abstract: *Pakistan is witnessing rural to urban migration because urban areas are comparatively advanced and are equipped with superior infrastructure than rural areas. This study has been designed mainly to compare the Purchasing Behavior between rural migrants of Sukkur and Khairpur districts. Primary data was collected using survey method from 383 rural migrants and data was analyzed by using Factor Analysis and Independent Samples Test. Factor Analysis results indicate that rural migrants of Sukkur and Khairpur districts while purchasing regard Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB), Purchasing Consciousness (PC), Enjoy Purchasing (EP), Income/ Pocket Money (INC/PM) and Price Consciousness/ Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC). Further results if Independent Samples Test suggested that all factors affecting Purchasing Behavior of r migrants in Sukkur district are significantly different than in Khairpur district. This study is helpful for companies and organizations as they can area difference in Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants and they can increase number of customers.*

Keywords: *Purchasing Behavior, Factors, Consciousness*

1.0 Introduction

Purchasing behavior has been a fruitful topic for researchers and is defined as a process that individuals or group of people espouse when they go to purchase and use any product, service and idea with a view to gratify their needs and wants. (Kotler & Keller, 2011). It is the mismatch in the infrastructure network, health and education services and many other factors between rural and urban areas creating a pressure on people to migrate to more facilitative areas of urban environment where they can enjoy these facilities (Devadas & Manohar, 2011). This is because people in villages perceive that they can lead a comparatively luxurious life in urban areas than in rural areas.

Many researchers have worked on Purchasing Behavior of consumers who are urban and who are rural separately. Further many researchers have also worked

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on comparison of migrants purchasing behavior between their rural and urban time. But a significant and well acceptable study was lacking in which comparison could have been made among the rural migrants of different areas and cities. To pursue this goal of understanding and comparing the purchasing behavior of rural migrants of different areas and cities this particular study has been designed. This study inculcates the dimension to compare Purchasing Behavior of customers who have migrated from rural areas to urban areas of two districts in Sukkur and Khairpur. Sukkur district is considered as more urbanized having more modern shopping and purchasing places and environment in comparison to Khairpur district. Few previous studies suggested that rural migrants have different factors like Switchover of brands, Consciousness to purchase and Consciousness to price and quality of a product, Purchase enjoyment and Income or pocket money affecting purchasing outcomes along with their behavior in urban environment (Devadas & Manohar, 2011) and (Ghumro, Dayo and Mangi, 2015). These factors may be different in two districts for migrants. This study is an attempt to see if there is any difference in the behavior of customers related to Purchasing with regards to migrants of two districts Sukkur and Khairpur comparatively.

1.1 Research Problem

Rural migrants can have different Purchasing Behavior if analyzed in different areas or cities (Devadas & Manohar, 2011). There is no renowned study on comparison of Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants among different areas or different cities. Research Problem in this study is to analyze if there is significant difference among migrants from rural areas with regards to their Purchase Behavior of district Sukkur and district Khairpur.

1.2 Objectives of Study

Study contains following objectives

- To understand the factors affecting and influencing on Purchasing Behavior migrants in both districts of Sukkur and Khairpur.
- To compare Purchasing Behavior among migrants of Sukkur and Khairpur districts.

1.3 Significance of Study

This study is significant because there is dearth of research work in which Purchase Behavior of migrants could have been understood by giving a comparison among different areas and cities. This dearth of studies in under developing and developing countries with regards to comparison of purchase behavior among two different areas particularly in case of rural migrants has been indicated in research of (Devadas & Manohar, 2011). As per our knowledge Pakistan has no renowned study on this subject in which purchasing behavior is observed in two different areas specially referring to rural migrants making this study automatically significant. Further this study is also significant because results of this study will help companies to analyze factors which are differently perceived by rural migrants of Sukkur and Khairpur districts as then they can

target those differentiating factors to retain and increase customers. Above mentioned signifying dimensions of this study adds value to the field of Purchasing Behavior.

2.0 Literature Review

Shih, Yu, and Tseng (2015) conducted established that purchase related behavior of rural migrants gets impacted by different characteristics that a product has. They further objectively concluded that different areas and cities can affect Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants differently as when change occurs in the environment of market. Ghumro, Dayo & Mangi (2015) said that migrants switch their existence brands, they start enjoying and showing eagerness to purchase, consider their income, price and quality while purchasing in urbanized environment.

Joshi et al. (2012) also talked about migrants Purchasing Behavior and found out that migrants are affected by price, quality, colorfulness and shape when they purchase. Zameer et al. (2012) approach towards purchasing along with factors impacting on purchase related behavior of migrants from rural areas. They found that their Purchasing Behavior has the tendency to change if the environment of the area changes. They further considered different factors like level that migrant is conscious in purchasing and enjoying the purchasing and pricing and qualitative products affect their behavior. Few extensively important researches were conducted on Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants who have migrated to urbanized environment leaving rural areas specially by (Devadas & Manohar, 2011). They found that migrants adopt different Purchasing Behavior depending on the area in which they have migrated. Further their study resulted that Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants is influenced by Switchover Behavior of brands. They also considered consciousness among migrants with regards to price and quality. Finally they also recommended Income along with level of consciousness to purchase and level of enjoyment in purchase as affecting factors on Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants. In the end they suggested to have comparative analysis of Purchasing behavior among customers of different areas because they said that there is difference among purchasing behavior of rural migrants among different areas. Hamid (2010) also analyzed switching of brands in rural migrants. Amanor-Boadu (2009) in his research resulted that Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants can be different if their area is changes depending the environment of the area. Sun and Wu (2004) found that enjoyment of purchasing and consciousness of purchasing effect the Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants. Lau-Gesk (2003) researched and concluded that Income can affect on Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants and overall Purchasing Behavior may be adjusted with change in the area where rural migrants are settled. Smith (1999) also supported past literature and concluded that Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants depends on price and quality of product and absence of these makes migrants to switch the brands. They also made a reference that migrants perceive factors of Purchasing Behavior differently in different areas.

2.1 Research Model

Figure 1: Research Model

Above model is taken with making it subject to modification considering the “American consumer satisfaction index model (2009)” framed in Michigan’s Business School and University. This model is signifying that Purchasing Behavior of migrants is influenced by Brand Switchover Behavior, Purchasing Consciousness, Enjoy Purchasing, Income/ Pocket Money and Price Consciousness/ Quality Consciousness.

2.2 Hypotheses of Study

Study has five hypotheses

H:1: Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB) of rural migrants of Khairpur district.

H:2: Purchasing Consciousness (PC) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Purchasing Consciousness (PC) of rural migrants of Khairpur district.

H:3: Enjoy Purchasing (EP) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Enjoy Purchasing (EP) of rural migrants of Khairpur district.

H:4: Income/ Pocket Money (INC/PM) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Income/ Pocket Money (INC/PM) of rural migrants of Khairpur district.

H:5: Price Consciousness/ Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Price Consciousness/Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC) of rural migrants of Khairpur district.

3.0 Methodology

Quantitative form of methodology was selected for this particular study. Population for the study contains rural migrants of Sukkur and Khairpur districts and period of their living is three to ten years and their estimated population is 100000 as data provided by District Authorities of Sukkur and Khairpur districts. Rural migrant Students male or female (Ranging from First year to Masters) who receive Pocket Money or are earning Income and taking purchase decision from colleges having age from 16 to above 20 years of Sukkur and Khairpur districts have been taken as Sample. Primary data has been used in this study and Convenient Sampling technique was applied to collect the data. Sample size was determined is 383 selected on the source of sample size table given by (Saunders et al., 2009) and resulting on formula by (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970). Questionnaire used in this study to collect data was adopted and modified questionnaire of (Devadas & Manohar, 2011).

4.0 Analysis and Result

Factor Analysis and Independent Sample test has been applied to analyze data.

4.1. Factor Analysis

Factor Analysis has been used and applied to see factors affecting rural migrants of Sukkur and Khairpur districts. Results are given below:

4.1.1 Factor Extraction

Table No. 01: Total Variance Explained (TVE)

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.640	17.599	17.599	2.640	17.599	17.599
2	2.261	15.074	32.672	2.261	15.074	32.672
3	1.656	11.037	43.710	1.656	11.037	43.710
4	1.513	10.088	53.798	1.513	10.088	53.798
5	1.253	8.352	62.149	1.253	8.352	62.149
6	.985	6.565	68.714			
7	.790	5.269	73.983			
8	.764	5.091	79.074			
9	.590	3.933	83.007			
10	.545	3.634	86.641			
11	.462	3.079	89.720			
12	.431	2.873	92.594			
13	.386	2.571	95.165			
14	.374	2.494	97.659			
15	.351	2.341	100.000			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.						

Above table results suggest that following the Eigen Values five factors have been extracted and used for more analysis and operations as five factors have Eigen Values equal or greater than 1. Five factors are explaining 62.149% of total variance.

4.1.2 Factor Rotation:

Factors have been rotated using VARIMAX rotation and its results are given in table no. 2:

Table No. 02: Rotated Component Matrix by Applying VARIMAX Rotation

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
BSB5	.724				
BSB2	.676				
BSB6	.632				
BSB1	.608				
BSB4	.595				
BSB3	.554				
EP2		.810			
EP3		.798			
EP1		.733			
INC/PM2			.871		
INC/PM1			.853		
PC1				.866	
PC2				.852	
PRCQC1					.883
PRCQC2					.856
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.					
a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.					

Strong loadings indicate that Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants of Sukkur and Khairpur districts is strongly influenced and affected by extracted five factors and its items.

4.2 Independent Samples Test

This test is applied to compare the mean difference among rural migrants of Sukkur and Khairpur districts with reference to factors affecting their Purchasing Behavior

Table No. 03: Independent Samples Test

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t-test for Equality of Means					
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
BSB	Equal variances assumed	5.424	.051	4.158	348	.000	.366	.088	.193	.539
	Equal variances not assumed			4.221	347.991	.000	.366	.087	.195	.536
PC	Equal variances assumed	.658	.418	-1.655	348	.039	-.182	.110	-.398	.034
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.654	337.531	.039	-.182	.110	-.398	.034
EP	Equal variances assumed	.007	.936	-.630	348	.029	-.061	.097	-.253	.130
	Equal variances not assumed			-.628	332.509	.531	-.061	.098	-.253	.131
INC/PM	Equal variances assumed	7.199	.058	-.343	348	.032	-.032	.094	-.217	.153
	Equal variances not assumed			-.336	297.727	.037	-.032	.096	-.221	.157
PRC/QC	Equal variances assumed	.880	.349	1.861	348	.024	.218	.117	-.012	.448
	Equal variances not assumed			1.855	332.910	.064	.218	.117	-.013	.449

Above test shows the results of Independent Sample T-Test. Section “Levene’s Test for Equality of Variances” shows insignificant results as $p > .05$ for all above mentioned variables suggesting that Equal Variances are assumed and first row results naming “Equal Variances are assumed” was used for all variables for further analysis. Furthermore all variables) have significant results ($p < .05$) in the section “t-test for equality of means” hence it can be concluded that mean difference for all variables of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different than rural migrants of Khairpur district. This significant difference among these factors may be because Sukkur district is much more facilitative and has built in with more advanced type of awareness tools than Khairpur district. Further migrants residing in Sukkur districts have more choices than Khairpur district because of the fact that market in Sukkur is much larger than Khairpur having different alternatives and choices available to people.

4.3. Results of Hypotheses

H:1: Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB) of rural migrants of Khairpur district.

Independent Samples Test result shows that Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB) has significant results ($p < .05$) in the section “t-test for equality of means” (See Table: 03) suggesting that mean difference for Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from rural migrants of Khairpur district. As mean difference for Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from rural migrants of Khairpur district so it can be concluded that Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Brand Switchover Behavior (BSB) of rural migrants of Khairpur district. So above mentioned hypothesis has been accepted and is same as resulted by

(Devadas & Manohar, 2011) and (Hamid, 2010).

H:2: Purchasing Consciousness (PC) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Purchasing Consciousness (PC) of rural migrants of Khairpur district.

Independent Samples Test result shows that Purchasing Consciousness (PC) has significant results ($p < .05$) in the section “t-test for equality of means” (See Table: 03) suggesting that mean difference for Purchasing Consciousness (PC) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from rural migrants of Khairpur district. As mean difference for Purchasing Consciousness (PC) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from rural migrants of Khairpur district so it can be concluded that Purchasing Consciousness (PC) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Purchasing Consciousness (PC) of rural migrants of Khairpur district. So above mentioned hypothesis has been accepted and is same as resulted by (Devadas & Manohar, 2011) and (Amanor-Boadu, 2009).

H:3: Enjoy Purchasing (EP) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Enjoy Purchasing (EP) of rural migrants of Khairpur district.

Independent Samples Test result shows that Enjoy Purchasing (EP) has significant results ($p < .05$) in the section “t-test for equality of means” (See Table: 03) suggesting that mean difference for Enjoy Purchasing (EP) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from rural migrants of Khairpur district. As mean difference for Enjoy Purchasing (EP) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from rural migrants of Khairpur district so it can be concluded that Enjoy Purchasing (EP) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Enjoy Purchasing (EP) of rural migrants of Khairpur district. So above mentioned hypothesis has been accepted and is same as resulted by (Devadas & Manohar, 2011) and (Sun & Wu, 2004).

H:4: Income/ Pocket Money (INC/PM) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Income/ Pocket Money (INC/PM) of rural migrants of Khairpur district.

Independent Samples Test result shows that Income/ Pocket Money (INC/PM) has significant results ($p < .05$) in the section “t-test for equality of means” (See Table: 03) suggesting that mean difference for Income/ Pocket Money (INC/PM) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from rural migrants of Khairpur district. As mean difference for Income/ Pocket Money (INC/PM) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from rural migrants of Khairpur district so it can be concluded that Income/ Pocket Money (INC/PM) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Income/ Pocket Money (INC/PM) of rural migrants of Khairpur district. So above mentioned hypothesis has been accepted and is same as resulted by (Devadas & Manohar, 2011) and (Lau-Gesk, 2003).

H:5: Price Consciousness/ Quality Consciousness(PRC/QC) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Price Consciousness/ Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC) of rural migrants of Khairpur district.

Independent Samples Test result shows that Price Consciousness/Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC) has significant results ($p < .05$) in the section “t-test for equality of means” (See Table: 03) suggesting that mean difference for Price Consciousness/Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from rural migrants of Khairpur district. As mean difference for Price Consciousness/Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from rural migrants of Khairpur district so it can be concluded that Price Consciousness/Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC) of rural migrants of Sukkur district is significantly different from Price Consciousness/Quality Consciousness (PRC/QC) of rural migrants of Khairpur district. So above mentioned hypothesis has been accepted and is same as resulted by (Devadas & Manohar, 2011) and (Smith, 1999).

5.0 Conclusion and Future Recommendations

Current study was conducted with a view to compare the purchase related behavior of migrants of Sukkur and Khairpur districts. These factors were tested in both districts and a comparison was made for purchase behavior on these factors in Sukkur and Khairpur district. Results revealed that all factors mentioned in research model affecting Purchasing Behavior of migrants of Sukkur district are significantly different than in Khairpur district. So it is concluded that rural migrants of Sukkur district and Khairpur district perceived (BSB), (PC), (EP), (INC/PM) and (PRC/QC) differently. This significant difference is more likely to occur because of presence of bigger and more competitive market in Sukkur district than in Khairpur district. People in Sukkur district are more exposed to triggering and appealing media along with information and awareness campaigns regarding products in comparison to Khairpur district. Market in Sukkur district also has more number of goods available along with different alternatives than market in Khairpur district causing the presence of significant difference in migrants of Sukkur and Khairpur districts. With these results companies and organizations can get an input regarding area difference with reference to Purchasing Behavior of rural migrants and they can further increase their customers and revenues. Future scholars and researchers should include other districts too along with respondents from different walks of life as to make the study more acceptable.

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